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Dynamic Modelling of a Rainwater Harvesting System for the YTL Development at Filton Airfield

**Water Innovation
& Research
Centre**

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

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17:00, 14th May 2020

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Abstract

Rainwater harvesting (RWH) is an important technology with potential to improve urban water security while also enhancing stormwater management by reducing the strain on downstream drainage networks after high rainfall events. In this project, a behavioural model for a RWH system was developed for use in a case study application at Filton Airfield in North Bristol. Two RWH systems were optimised (a centralised and decentralised system) by assessing the influence of tank storage capacity, set point and operating algorithm (YAS and YBS) on 3 performance indicators: water savings efficiency, storm capture efficiency and loss factor. Two rainfall regimes and a standard weekly demand profile formed the inputs of the model. Results show that the tank storage capacity is the most significant determinant of system performance for both approaches. In comparison, setpoint has a minimal effect on performance, although this was because of a lack of high-resolution rainfall data. The choice of operating algorithm was found to have no considerable effect on performance. Once optimised, the decentralised system exhibits better performance due to a higher catchment-demand ratio which equates to greater cost savings from reduced mains usage. Although the decentralised system offers a better return on investment, it only serves 8.3% of the demand served by the centralised system; therefore, the effect from economies of scale may render the centralised system as the best choice for the case study. These results provided reference for an optimisation approach of RWH systems used to improve water savings and stormwater reduction performance for the urban development at Filton Airfield.

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1 Introduction

In 2015, the United Nations declared, 'Ensuring availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all' as one of its 17 Sustainable Development Goals which form a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet. The sustainable management of water resources is a global challenge with significant implications for the prosperity, development and health of humankind. Urban environments present the greatest obstacle to this challenge, where changes to hydrology, greater water demand and the effects of climate change all act in tandem, placing stress on urban water management systems.

Rainwater harvesting is an age-old technology, dating back as early as 2600 BC with evidence of tanks being used to collect rainwater by the Indus Valley Civilisation (Pandey et al., 2003). Despite its ancient inception, interest in rainwater harvesting for use in developed urban environments has continued to rise over the past decade with increased research output and the establishment and planning of RWH projects in the Netherlands, Spain and Italy (Hofman & Paalman, 2014; Morales-Pinzón et al., 2012; Napoli et al., 2014). The proliferation of RWH from city to city can be attributed to the potential RWH has to reduce mains water demand and to attenuate flooding in a more cost-effective way than the scale-up of existing systems, which is the traditional approach that is often followed even at great expense due to the pervasive nature of these systems. The inherent simplicity of rainwater harvesting allows for quick and low-cost implementation into new or existing water management systems. Despite this, the case for the economic viability of RWH projects is often called into question, largely stemming from a difficulty in assessment of the cost-savings derived from flood attenuation. The scale of RWH systems can vary considerably; they can be as small as a roof catchment system serving a single house all the way up to a centralised system distributing rainwater to hundreds of houses across a wide area.

In summary, the combined effect of urbanisation on hydrology paired with the threats to water security and elevated flood risk highlights the need to investigate RWH as part of a novel approach to urban water management in the 21st century and to assess its suitability for use in ongoing urban developments.

2 Literature Review

2.1 – Global trends in urbanisation

At present, urbanisation is one of the most significant global trends; there has been uninterrupted, net-positive emigration from rural to urban areas throughout the 20th and early 21st century (United Nations Population Division, 2018). A dramatic paradigm shift at such a scale has profound effects on global economic development, energy consumption, urban water management and human well-being (Chen et al., 2014; Cox et al., 2018; Foster, 1990; Wang, 2014). The past few decades have been characterised as the most rapid period of urban growth in human history – this trend is set to continue as 2.3 billion additional urban dwellers are expected by 2050 (United Nations Population Division, 2018). Much of this increase is focussed in water-scarce regions, notably the Middle East and Northern Africa (Richey et al., 2015; United Nations Population Division, 2019). Increased stress on urban water management systems represents one of the most prominent barriers to global urban development, particularly in water-scarce regions; a novel approach is required (Farrelly & Brown, 2011; Van de Meene et al., 2011).

2.2 – The effect of urbanisation on water demand

The effect of urbanisation on water demand must be considered. Sazakli et al. (2007) provides evidence to demonstrate that current water management in urban environments is far from being sustainable, giving rise to tension between urban water supply and demand. This tension has two primary drivers: growing domestic water consumption and the inability to further reduce industrial water use (Wu and Tan, 2012). The progression towards urbanisation will exacerbate the stresses on water management systems. Moreover, the economic development that generally accompanies urbanisation will compound the effect of increased municipal water demand – especially in rapidly-developing economies.

The availability of new technologies such as dishwashers, washing machines and domestic irrigation systems as well as the resulting demand for a higher standard of living from the typical urban dweller will increase municipal water use on a per-capita basis (Domene & Saurí, 2006; Parker & Wilby, 2013). Furthermore, this increase in municipal water demand is also driven by a propensity for economic development to increase the fraction of the urban population that

uses the municipal supply rather than other sources such as local wells or private water vendors (McDonald et al., 2014).

2.3 – Hydrology of urban environments

Urbanisation causes the alteration of natural landscapes through soil compaction, the creation of impervious surfaces, land grading and the removal of vegetation; thus, it has a dramatic effect on landscape hydrology and by extension, increases flood risks (Barron et al., 2013; McGrane, 2016; Nirupama & Simonovic, 2007). These changes typically result in increased stormwater runoff rates and volumes as well as the decrease in groundwater infiltration (Shuster et al., 2005). Although a comparative hydrological analysis of urban environments may yield quantitative information on the strength of certain approaches, its scope is limited as no commonly accepted universal metric for urban expansion exists. Instead, multiple studies have used total impervious area or population density as proxies for urban area (MacGregor-Fors, 2011).

Infrastructure flows have traditionally been separated from natural hydrological analysis, however, due to increased awareness that inefficient elements of urban water systems lead to an influx of water and contaminants to natural systems, research is moving towards the integration of these two cycles to provide a more holistic understanding of the impact of urbanisation on natural hydrological systems (Leung & Jiao, 2006). With better integration of these two systems, it is hoped that stormwater can be managed more effectively to reduce peak intensity (i.e., flood risk) and satisfy the water demand of urban dwellers.

2.4 – The effect of climate change on flooding

Climate change is a driver for the increased frequency and severity of hydrometeorological events. This trend has direct implications for flood management, specifically in urban environments. Traditional approaches to the design and operation of urban stormwater management systems have been predicated on the historical dynamics of natural hydrological systems and the ability to extrapolate this performance together with the performance of urban stormwater management systems across their operational lifetime (Adams & J, 2000). However, research by Huong and Pathirana (2013) challenges this thinking by highlighting the effect of climate variability and climate change on risk that lead to flooding – particularly in urban environments. Consequently, Ashley et al. (2005) argue that it is incumbent on designers and operators of storm drainage systems to prepare for greater uncertainty in the effectiveness

of storm drainage systems and that flood risks may increase by a factor of almost 30 due to the potential effects of climate and socio-economic change.

Climate change at the global scale is not the only driver of meteorological uncertainty. Urban microclimates impact the artificial thermal properties and increased particulate matter from urban areas which affect the way rainfall is generated and enhance downwind precipitation and may enhance the generation of convective summer thunderstorms (Jin & Shepherd, 2005). In response to these trends, rainwater harvesting is identified as a sustainable strategy with the potential for flood attenuation, reduced external water demand and as a measure against periodic water scarcity Farreny et al. (2011).

3 Case Study, Model Development and Simulation Methods

3.1 – Context and situation of the Filton Airfield development

The details of the YTL development at Filton Airfield in North Bristol must be considered in order to produce a model that provides actionable recommendations for the design and optimisation of RWH systems. The comparison between centralised and decentralised systems is a focal area of this report and such an analysis necessitates a detailed understanding of the suitability and implementation of each system.

Figure 3.1. Filton Airfield Master Plan (YTL, 2019).

The Filton Airfield master plan, labelled Fig. 3.1, denotes the current land arrangement by planned usage. It encompasses an area of 141.79 hectares. Of interest in this project are the residential areas, marked as grey, and the Brabazon Hangars (mixed use, non-residential), marked red in the southwest of the diagram. **The central Brabazon Hangar is set to be repurposed into an arena for the purpose of holding music, sports and other events with a capacity of 17,080 people and with one million annual visitors expected. Possessing a total estimated catchment area of 10,000m², it offers an ideal location for a centralised RWH system (YTL, 2015).** This centralised system would involve a single tank at the arena site. Residential housing offers the potential for decentralised RWH systems which would exist in larger numbers, with each system serving a small number of houses. **The proposed development contains 2,675 residential units, although because there is little information on the percentage of apartments and semi-detached and fully detached units, a mean catchment area of 65m² per unit is assumed.** Since the development is to occur procedurally, a group of **278 houses** is to be considered in this report. The decentralised approach would involve multiple RWH systems, each serving a connected group of houses. **Based on the proposed adoptable drainage layout,**

each tank is assumed to serve a group of 23 houses, hence the catchment area per tank for the decentralised system is 1,495m².

3.2 – Algorithm and schematics for RWH systems

To assess the feasibility of RWH systems in the YTL development, a generalised model may be used for both centralised and decentralised approaches. Below are key definitions for parameters and variables used to model RWH systems. Rainfall (R_i) represents the rainfall incident on the catchment surface. Harvested rainwater (Q_i) represents the volume of rainwater harvested from the catchment area. Volume (V_i) represents the volume of harvested rainwater stored within the tank. Yield (Y_i) represents the volume of harvested rainwater (stored within the tank) that is used to satisfy demand. Mains (M_i) represents the volume of water (supplied by the mains network) needed to meet demand if yield is insufficient. Demand (D_i) represents the volume of water supplied to household appliances which is met by either yield, mains or some combination of the two. Spillage (O_i) represents the volume of harvested rainwater diverted to a drainage network due to zero spare storage within the tank. For all the above variables, i is the time step of the model where each time step is separated by a constant time interval. Fig. 3.2 contains the schematic for a conventional, on-site RWH system. Indicated on the schematic are parameters as well as the fluxes between catchment, tank, appliances and the drainage network.

Figure 3.2. Schematic for a conventional, on-site RWH system (Hofman & Paalman, 2014).

Fig. 3.3 contains the pseudocode, represented diagrammatically with a flowchart, that was used as the basis for development of the tank volume model. It shows the operations computed and the statements executed at each time step – it follows the YBS algorithm of a RWH system.

Figure 3.3. Flowchart displaying the computations executed at each timestep of the model (YBS variant).

3.3 – Inflow to the RWH tank

Inflow to the tank was calculated with Eq. 1, where ϕ is the runoff coefficient and A is the total area of the catchment surface.

$$Q_i = \phi \cdot R_i \cdot A \tag{1}$$

Runoff coefficient is a dimensionless factor that is used to convert the rainfall amounts to runoff. It represents the integrated effect of catchment losses. Consideration must be given to

the type of surface, slope, degree of saturation and rainfall intensity when specifying the runoff coefficient for a given surface (Goel, 2011). The recommended runoff value for typical urban roofing used to determine the volumetric inflow is 0.95 (American Society of Civil Engineers, 1952). The filter coefficient attempts to account for rainwater lost over the filter as harvested rainwater moves from the catchment area to the storage tank. With proper system maintenance, the effect of the filter on the flow is negligible. However, decentralised systems are more difficult to maintain as sizeable differences in filter performance may arise over the lifetime of RWH systems. Furthermore, filter performance is dependent on water quality, data for which was not available. For these reasons, the effect of filter performance on the volume of harvested rainwater was not considered. It is assumed that the tank is covered, thus losses due to evaporation are negligible. The general balance for a RWH system is described by Eq. 2.

$$V_i = V_{i-1} + Q_i - S_i - Y_i \tag{2}$$

3.4 – Yield before spillage and yield after spillage models

Figure 3.4. Schematic representation of the **YAS** behavioural model with arrows denoting inflows and outflows to the tank.

Figure 3.5. Schematic representation of the **YBS** behavioural model with arrows denoting inflows and outflows to the tank.

Fig. 3.4 and Fig 3.5. show the Yield After Spillage (YAS) and Yield Before Spillage (YBS) models for a RWH system developed by Jenkins et al., 1978. These models represent either extreme of a modelling assumption relating to when harvested rainwater is used. In each case, three calculations are computed at each timestep.

Starting with the **YAS model** in Fig. 3.3: firstly, the total inflow into the tank is added to the stored volume at the previous time step. Secondly, the water volume that exceeds tank capacity (i.e., spillage) is calculated and subtracted. Finally, yield, is then accounted for, providing the

stored volume at the current timestep. This is represented below by Eq. 3 and 4 (Fewkes & Butler, 2000).

$$Y_i = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} D_i \\ V_{i-1} \end{matrix} \right. \quad [3]$$

$$V_i = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} V_{i-1} + Q_i - Y_i \\ S - Y_i \end{matrix} \right. \quad [4]$$

In both models, yield equates to demand insofar as the demand does not exceed the stored tank volume. In the case where demand exceeds stored tank volume (i.e., the tank is fully drained), water from the mains is used to ensure demand is fully met. **The YBS model follows** the same computations as the YAS model except that yield is accounted for before excess rainwater is spilled. This is represented below by Eq. 5 and 6.

$$Y_i = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} D_i \\ V_{i-1} + Q_i \end{matrix} \right. \quad [5]$$

$$V_i = \min \left\{ \begin{matrix} V_{i-1} + Q_i - Y_i \\ S \end{matrix} \right. \quad [6]$$

3.5 – Active and Passive RWH systems

The British Standards Institute defines active RWH management as systems where the stored water volume is managed to maintain spare storage for the eventuality of a large storm to ensure the runoff is stored (British Standards Institute, 2009). To achieve this, a setpoint for tank level is selected to maintain this spare storage. Conversely, in passive RWH systems the storing and emptying of water in a tank (or spilling when full) is a function of demand. Current research from Behzadian et al., 2018 provides simulations which show that the best performing conventional (or passive) RWH solution with maximum flood attenuation performance (approximately an 85% reduction in excess stormwater) requires 46% of full-size tank capacity of a conventional design. Active RWH systems greatly improve upon this, requiring only 19% of full-size tank capacity of a conventional design and clearly showing active systems to be far more cost effective than passive ones. Although active systems have a lower yield-to-demand ratio, this does not constrain the opportunity to use rainwater harvesting for stormwater management, irrespective of the uncertainty of their occupancy levels (British Standards Institute, 2009).

Weather forecasting is an alternate form of active RWH management whereby the forecasting of a high rainfall event prevents the tank from emptying if the event is due within 6 hours. Additionally, **if a significant event is currently happening or has happened in the last 24 hours**

the tank is prevented from emptying. This approach maintains spare storage by only emptying harvested rainwater from the tank if it does not increase the risk of flooding by overloading the downstream drainage system. Although effective, this approach requires systems to be network-controlled in order to adjust spare storage in anticipation of rainfall events. Active systems are more technically demanding requiring complex measuring or network devices; despite this, they are hydrologically much more complete and efficient (Kinkade-Levario, 2007). For this reason, the model used for this report will be based on active rainwater harvesting through use of a setpoint for tank level. Most of the utility of rainwater harvesting is derived from flood attenuation and when compared to passive systems, active systems offer greater performance for the same value.

3.6 – Threshold rainfall rate

The literature indicates that flood attenuation performance may confer the greatest cost-saving benefits (Hofman & Paalman, 2014), therefore the conventional model was adapted to better deal with extreme rainfall events, which are the primary driver of flooding. RWH systems attenuate flooding by diverting rainwater from stormwater sewers into storage tanks during extreme rainfall events. This reduces peak inflow to the stormwater sewers, thus reducing the likelihood of flooding. This functionality is reliant upon the presence of available storage capacity during an extreme event which is what a set point accomplishes; it specifies a maximum tank level to ensure the presence of available storage for such events. However, this model will encounter issues with extreme events that last for multiple timesteps as it would result in the spillage of stored rainwater above the setpoint during an extreme event, increasing the inflow to stormwater systems – the opposite of the intended effect. To correct for this, the model was amended to assess whether current rainfall was above a threshold value before spillage. If the rate of rainfall is below this value, the risk of flooding is low and the tank spills excess rainwater until it reaches the setpoint. Conversely, if the rate of rainfall is above this value, there is at least a moderate risk of flooding and the tank will store harvested rainwater beyond the setpoint until maximum capacity is reached. This functionality reduces the risk of flooding or attenuates the effects if flooding cannot be avoided. Based on available historical data this threshold rate was set at 10mm day⁻¹.

3.7 – Performance indicators for RWH systems

Water savings efficiency (E_{WS}) is the percentage of non-potable demand that is met by harvested rainwater. Water savings efficiency quantifies the water conservation performance of RWH systems (Haque et al., 2016; Wallace et al., 2015). **Water savings efficiency** tends towards 100% when harvested rainwater is able to fully satisfy demand and it is defined according to Eq. 7.

$$E_{WS} = \frac{\sum Y_i}{\sum D_i} \cdot 100 \quad [7]$$

Stormwater capture efficiency (E_{SC}) is the percentage of stormwater generated from the catchment which is used to satisfy non-potable water demand (Zhang & Guo, 2013). In essence, the stormwater capture efficiency is identical to the water savings efficiency expect for spillage; storm capture accounts for spillage whilst water savings does not and thus it can be used to assess the effect of the RWH system on downstream drainage networks. It quantifies the runoff reduction performance and may be calculated through use of Eq. 8 (Zhang et al., 2020).

$$E_{SC} = \frac{\sum Y_i}{\sum \phi A \cdot \frac{R_i}{1000}} \cdot 100 \quad [8]$$

Campisano & Modica, 2014 define **retention efficiency (E_R)** according to Eq. 9 which evaluates the volumetric retention performance of the tank. The loss factor (L_F), a new indicator based on the retention efficiency is defined according to Eq. 10. Instead of retention, the loss factor measures spillage from the tank (due to overflow and the setpoint) relative to the total volume of harvested rainwater. The loss factor tends towards 100% when the sum of overflow discharges (Q_{Di}) tends towards the total volume of harvested rainwater. This is commonly the case in systems with small tanks and reduced demand.

$$E_R = \left[1 - \frac{\sum Q_{Di}}{\sum \phi A \cdot \frac{R_i}{1000}} \right] \cdot 100 \quad [9]$$

$$L_F = \left[\frac{\sum Q_{Di}}{\sum A \cdot R_i} \right] \cdot 100 \quad [10]$$

YAS models underestimate RWH system performance as the determination of spillage prior to yield reduces the effective storage capacity of the RWH tank whilst YBS overestimate RWH system performance since yield does not perfectly coincide with rain-induced tank overflow – this is an idealised case. Zhang et al., 2020 simulated both YAS and YBS models, comparing the E_{WS} , E_{SC} and reliability finding that as the time series length of simulation increases, the

difference between the indicator values obtained using short-term simulation periods and the longer reference period reduces.

3.8 – Simulation of rainfall

Throughout the preliminary stages of development, a placeholder approximation was used for daily rainfall, represented by the variable X , which was normally distributed around a mean of 10mm. Once generated, X was appended to an array containing the previously generated values. Consequently, the tank volume model was run using this array of values to simulate rainfall. This approach to rainfall simulation was taken to ensure the tank volume model functioned as intended – once this was established, a more sophisticated and real-world approach to rainfall simulation was taken. A time series containing an 11-year-long set of daily rainfall values in the Bristol region for approximately 4000 consecutive days from the 1st of January 2008 until the 31st of December 2018 was used as an input to replace the rudimentary placeholder approximation described above. This approach allowed for the demonstration of the tank volume model with real-world, region-specific rainfall data.

Given that the RWH systems in urban settings are beginning to form part of a more holistic, decentralised approach to urban stormwater management systems, it is important to consider resilience and long-term applicability when optimising design parameters (Valdez et al., 2016). Consequently, proposed RWH systems must be designed with the capacity to withstand and manage extreme events. Given the typical operational lifetime of a RWH system, an extreme event that occurs once in 30 years should be accounted for (Ghimire et al., 2019). An 11-year-long historical set should not be used to simulate a once-in-30-year event due to the limitations of extrapolating a data set beyond a reasonable scope. Hence probabilistic modelling must be employed.

Weather events can be simulated by either *deterministic* or *stochastic* models. The word “stochastic” implies the presence of a random variable; e.g. stochastic variation is variation in which at least one of the elements is a variate and a *stochastic process* is one wherein the system incorporates an element of randomness as opposed to a *deterministic system*. In a deterministic model, the values for the dependent variables of the system are entirely determined by the parameters of the model. In contrast, *stochastic*, or *probabilistic*, models include *randomness* in such a way that the outputs of the model take the form of probability distributions rather than discrete values (Rey, 2015). Rainfall is a complex phenomenon driven by multiple physical

mechanisms acting at multiple spatio-temporal scales; thus, deterministic modelling holds limited practical value for the purpose of rainfall simulation (Hingray & Ben Haha, 2005). More specifically, Hingray and Ben Haha, 2005, through an analysis of seven disaggregation models, show that classic deterministic models lead to a significant underestimation of some important rainfall statistics such as variation coefficient and extremes of 10-min rainfall amounts. Stochastic models have been the standard for several decades where the model outcomes are non-discretised (Rey, 2015). Instead, they are probability distributions, or density functions, which represent the inherent statistical properties of a phenomenon. Koutsoyiannis and Pachakis, 1996, demonstrate the efficacy of such models at simulating rainfall by showing there to be no substantial difference in behaviour between a synthetic and historic rainfall time series.

Kurothe et al., 1997 provides evidence to show that the intensity of daily rainfall levels is distributed exponentially if only wet days (days with rainfall) are considered. To allow for the modelling approach described by the flowchart in Fig. 3.5, two assumptions were made. Firstly, daily rainfall levels were assumed to be exponentially distributed for wet days only. Secondly, the probability of a day without rainfall occurring is equal to the total number of ‘dry days’ divided by the total number of days in the time series. **For the 11-year-long set of daily rainfall values this probability was found to be 0.47.** With these two modelling assumptions, synthetic rainfall time series could be generated using the simulation steps described below.

Figure 3.5. Flowchart displaying the process for generating synthetic rainfall data from a historical time series.

Firstly, the 11-year-long set of daily rainfall values was manipulated by omitting all dry days from the data set to only include days with non-zero rainfall levels. **The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS test) is a distribution-fitting algorithm that quantifies the extent to which a dataset adheres to an empirical distribution. The KS test outputs the location and scale parameters for the probability distribution which most closely matches the dataset as well as the p-value which indicates the probability that this pattern was due to a random sampling error. After the application of the KS test (distribution fit), the inherent statistical properties of the historical time series are represented by a probability (continuous) distribution using the location and scale parameters. Subsequently, a Monte Carlo simulation can be applied to yield different sets**

of rainfall data or 'paths' of this stochastic process through iteration with a set of random variables or 'state space' modelled on the basis of the probability distribution produced in the previous step.

3.9 – Simulation of demand

With the development of the RWH model and the rainfall simulation, the final step was the generation of a non-potable domestic water demand time series. Non-potable domestic water demand generally follows a cyclical demand profile as the behavioural habits of humans lead to a pattern of surges, drops and stable levels throughout the day. For instance, after getting up in the morning most people use the toilet, resulting in a surge in water demand, however, this is an oversimplified picture – in reality, factors such as day of the week and the age and gender of residents have a measurable effect on this demand profile and consequently consideration must be given to these factors.

An objective of this project was to analyse the efficacy of both centralised and decentralised RWH systems. This requires non-potable water demand profiles for the centralised system (supplied by the central Brabazon Hangar) and decentralised system (supplied by groups of 23 residential units). SIMDEUM, a MATLAB program developed by the KWR Water Research Institute was used to produce these demand profiles. SIMDEUM utilises a '.SPG' file that contains pre-determined values and data supplied by the user to create '.stats' files which contain the water demand profile for up to a week-long period. Harvested rainwater is non-potable, therefore only water demand from toilet and washing machine usage was taken into account. Water demand is affected by seasonal weather, e.g., increased water use for irrigation during summer months; however, SIMDEUM only provides demand profiles for periods of up to a week thus the effect of seasonal weather on demand profiles is not accounted for. Despite this limitation, it should have a negligible effect on non-potable demand profiles as they are not subject to variance due to seasonal weather. Since demand was simulated for a single week, the RWH model replicated the profile to match the length of the simulation.

Since the Filton Site is in development, precise data for the number of residents in each unit is not yet available. Without this data, accurate simulation of water demand is more difficult, and although the percentages of one-person, two-person and multi-person households are known (25.5%, 33.8% and 40.7% respectively). It should be noted that this does not necessarily reflect the actual number of residents in each unit. Furthermore, given the stage of development, the

demographic information of residents is not available. It is assumed that there would be negligible bias of age, gender and employment for future Filton residents from the Dutch residents upon which the defaults are based. Therefore, the default values contained in the demo files were used and the composition of housing types was altered to reflect the balance of one-person, two-person and multi-person households provided by YTL. As mentioned in the Project Planning and Design section, with additional time for data collection, accurate demographic information for future Filton residents may have been obtained from YTL.

The demand profiles for the centralised system (278 residential units) and the decentralised system (23 units) were exported from SIMDEUM as .csv files and input into the RWH model. The annual demand for the centralised and decentralised systems amounted to 15,412m³ and 1,275m³ respectively.

4 Project Planning and Design

4.1 – *Project aims and objectives*

The aim of this project is to produce a dynamic model for a rainwater harvesting system for the YTL urban development at Filton Airfield, optimise it and analyse its flood attenuation and mains water savings performance, consequently evaluating the economic feasibility of the project. The following objectives were set in order to meet this aim.

1. Development of a RWH system model in Python with reuse potential for future developments with potential for RWH system implementation.
2. Optimisation of RWH performance and system parameters including tank volume, setpoint, water saving efficiency, storm capture efficiency and **loss factor**.
3. Development of a simulation to generate synthetic rainfall data from a continuous distribution (stochastic process) based on a historical time series of daily rainfall values.
4. **Comparative analysis of centralised and decentralised RWH systems.**
5. Comparative analysis of YAS and YBS models.
6. Use of economic indicators to assess the economic viability and cost-saving benefits of an optimised RWH system in the YTL development.

4.2 – *Effects of the restriction on data collection*

The stoppage of data collection beyond the 17th of March hampered certain areas of the project. Firstly, the data collection trip to Filton Airfield could no longer take place. This meant no area-specific rain meter readings could be obtained. Under normal circumstances, these readings would have been cross-referenced with the North Bristol rainfall data to ensure its applicability to the YTL development. Secondly, the lack of data on stormwater sewer capacity prevented detailed analysis of the economic effect of flood attenuation performance – although the volume of water diverted away from stormwater sewers during an extreme event could be calculated, the effect of this diversion on flood risk or damage requires that the capacity of the sewer system is known. With additional time, this data may have been obtainable. If data collection had not ceased on the 17th of March, YTL may have been able to provide demographic data for expected residents at the Filton site. This data could have been used with the SIMDEUM to better estimate the non-potable domestic water demand profile.

The threshold value for rainfall rate which, if exceeded, would cause the RWH system to fill beyond the setpoint could not be adequately optimised. Optimisation of this value is a trade-off between improved flood attenuation performance (lower threshold) and better adherence to the setpoint volume (higher threshold). To optimise this parameter, high-resolution rainfall data is needed due to the potential of extreme events to last for a short period of time – daily rainfall data will average the rainfall of a short but extreme event across a 24-hour period. This would result in the threshold not being reached even though the threshold would be reached with hourly rainfall data. This data would have been available to use under normal circumstances. Finally, analysis of the synthetic data produced by the rainfall simulation revealed large inaccuracies between synthetic and historical rainfall data as periodicity and seasonality were not accounted for. With additional time, seasonal variance could have been built into the model by bifurcating the year into sections based on monthly rainfall trends; however, it is unlikely that the lack of periodicity could have been addressed due to the second modelling assumption in the development of the rainfall simulation which fixes the probability of wet and dry days.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 – Rainfall simulation

The efficacy of the distribution-fitting and Monte Carlo simulations were analysed to ensure that the inputs to the tank volume model were consistent with typical rainfall patterns of the North Bristol region which encompasses Filton Airfield. Rainfall events, patterns and behaviours may be described by **a plethora of metrics**. Within the context of this enquiry as it relates to the applicability of RWH systems to a development at Filton Airfield, **five key metrics** were identified **as necessary components of a thorough comparison of synthetic and historical rainfall data**. These metrics are **the distribution of rainfall event intensity, total annual rainfall, peak annual rainfall, seasonality and periodicity**. This analysis is comprised of a comparative analysis of rainfall data from between 2008 and 2018 with a year-long synthetic time series.

Figure 5.1. Histogram displaying the distribution of daily rainfall levels – excluding dry days – for Bristol from 1st January 2008 to 31st December 2018.

Figure 5.2. Histogram displaying the distribution of daily rainfall levels – excluding dry days – for a year-long period that were generated stochastically based on the time series presented in Fig. 5.1.

The distribution of rainfall events was assessed through a side-by-side, qualitative comparison of Fig. 5.1 and 5.2. Both time series appear to be distributed **exponentially** – this is expected since **the synthetic time series displayed in Fig. 5.1 reflects the inherent statistical properties of the historical time series in Fig. 5.2**. Given the assumption that rainfall levels for wet days are exponentially distributed, **the KS test may be applied to yield the p-value which was used to quantify the validity of this assumption**. The KS test yields a p-value of 0.027; thus, **the probability that this pattern was due to a random sampling error is sufficiently low**. The KS test **provided location and scale parameters of 0.254 and 3.85 respectively**. **These parameters describe an exponential distribution with the best-possible fit to the historical data, i.e., the distribution in Fig. 5.2 is the best-possible representation of the inherent statistical properties of the historical data insofar as it can be assumed that the historical data is distributed**

exponentially. This assumption is valid due to the p-value from the KS test, and consequently the synthetic time series accurately reflects the distribution of rainfall event intensity.

Annual rainfall averaged 706mm per year with a peak of 1135mm in 2012 and a low of 585mm in 2010 over the 11-year period from 2008 to 2019. This year-on-year variability is not apparent in the synthetic time series since each set is based off the same probability distribution – it is only the random nature of the input variables that results in variance. The overall average of mean annual rainfall for a set of ten synthetic time series was 729mm which is within $\pm 2.5\%$ of the real-world figure. As expected, there was little year-on-year variance with a peak of 743mm and a low of 717mm. The similarities in mean annual rainfall between historic and synthetic data demonstrate the general accuracy of the simulation, however, the lack of exceptionally wet years in the synthetic data (due to the low year-on-year variance) limit the applicability of such data. RWH system parameters need to be optimised with both typical and high-rainfall years since this will have a direct effect on flood attenuation performance – the main cost saving benefit of RWH systems.

Figure 5.3. Daily rainfall levels for Bristol from 1st January 2018 to 31st December 2018.

Figure 5.4. Daily rainfall levels for a year-long period that were generated stochastically based on a time series of rainfall values from 2008 to 2018.

Peak annual rainfall is the amount of rainfall experienced on the wettest day of a calendar year. In the synthetic time series, the peak annual rainfall was 24.1mm and 29.5mm for the historical as shown in Fig. 5.3 and Fig. 5.4 respectively. The peak annual rainfall for each of the other years was analysed to ensure this discrepancy was not due to an abnormal year. From this, it was found that as a mean, peak annual rainfall in the historic time series was 24% greater than in the synthetic time series. Although the historical data may be closely approximated by an exponential distribution, it is not a perfect fit. This is the cause of discrepancies between peak annual rainfall values in historic and synthetic time series. This discrepancy was more

pronounced when looking at extreme rainfall events. I.e., the rainfall values of common events are within $\pm 5\%$ of each other for historic and synthetic time series, however, for extreme events this difference is significant since the adherence to exponentiality decreases as events become less frequent. The histogram of rainfall events in Fig. 5.2 shows this deviation from exponentiality at high rainfall values (greater than 15mm). For this reason, a fitted exponential distribution will be unable to produce synthetic time series with similar peak annual rainfall values.

Seasonal variance is a key characteristic of rainfall that affects the distribution of wet and dry months throughout the year. Fig. 5.5 contains the mean monthly rainfall from 2008 until 2019 and exhibits seasonal variance with significantly wetter months from September to January and drier months from February to August. Although this data is specific to the Bristol region, this reduction in rainfall during the summer period is consistent with national rainfall data. Fig. 5.6 shows the mean monthly rainfall for data produced by the simulation which does not account for seasonal variance and as a result, month-on-month variance does not exceed $\pm 3.5\%$ from a mean of 66.8mm.

Figure 5.5. Monthly average rainfall for the Bristol region from 2008 to 2019.

Figure 5.6. Monthly average rainfall for synthetic rainfall data produced by the simulation (11-year aggregates).

Thus, the simulation underestimates monthly rainfall totals from September to January and overestimates these totals from February to August. This limitation has significant implications for the optimisation of RWH system parameters – namely, it may lead to an underestimation of the overall tank volume since parameters optimised using the synthetic data (found in Fig. 5.2 and 5.4) do not account for the high-rainfall months from September to January. I.e., RWH systems that are optimised for an inflow from 66.8 mm of rainfall per month will likely be unable to manage greater inflows caused by the effect of seasonality on rainfall.

As a metric, the periodicity of rainfall has important implications for the design and optimisation of RWH systems, specifically the impact of periodicity on the reliability of storage systems (Afzal et al., 2016). As stated earlier in this report, the periodicity of rainfall is not accounted for due to an assumption made during modelling – specifically that a rainfall event has a 47% chance to occur on any given day. The longest annual dry periods were 18 days and 7 days for the 2018 data and the synthetic data displayed in Fig. 5.3 and Fig. 5.4 respectively. Moreover, inspection of these graphs show dry periods to be more sustained and frequent in the historical rainfall data compared to the synthetic data. This stark difference is a result of the modelling assumption mentioned prior as the probability of rainfall on any given day is function of complex meteorological conditions and not a constant value of 47%. Since the simulation cannot accurately model dry periods, the RWH model will have a steadier influx of rainwater when operated using synthetic data. This feature will result in the artificial inflation of RWH system reliability as the RWH tank is less likely to be empty. When operated with historical data, dry periods have a far more prominent effect on the dynamics of the tank water level, with a higher likelihood for an empty tank, necessitating mains water usage and consequently reducing performance. **This difference in tank volume behaviour for historic and synthetic rainfall data is demonstrated in Fig. 5.7 and Fig. 5.8 which report the tank volume over a month-long period for both historical and stochastic rainfall data with the centralised RWH system.** Evidently the tank volume in Fig. 5.8 does not accurately simulate the tank volume based on real-world data because of the rainfall simulation method. Without accounting for periodicity, rainfall levels from the simulation are highly erratic and therefore so is the tank volume. Considering all the above, historical rainfall data is best suited for RWH parameter optimisation due to the limitations of the rainfall simulation at replicating the inherent statistical properties of the historical data.

Figure 5.7. Variance of tank volume for a month-long period with rainfall data from October 2018 with an hourly temporal scale.

Figure 5.8. Variance of tank volume for a month-long period with synthetic rainfall data with an hourly temporal scale.

In summary, although probabilistic modelling encompasses possible extreme rainfall events not within the scope of an 11-year-long data set, the synthetic data was inaccurate since the periodicity and seasonality of rainfall were not taken into account. RWH tank parameters were optimised with rainfall data from 2018 which is a typical year with mean annual rainfall of 706mm, within 2% of the mean. Subsequently, the optimised system was stress-tested using rainfall data from November 2009 (the wettest year of the available historical data, mean annual rainfall of 1135mm) to assess the resilience of the optimised system to adverse conditions.

5.2 – Demand simulation

Fig. 5.9 reports the demand profile generated by SIMDEUM. As expected, there is a surge of demand each morning that reaches a peak of $4.25\text{m}^3\text{ hr}^{-1}$. Demand falls during the day and rises again during the evening reaching a lower peak of $2.80\text{m}^3\text{ hr}^{-1}$ before dropping to a minimum at night. This pattern repeats itself throughout each weekday. On weekend the demand profile is similar except for increased demand in the afternoon and evening. This profile constitutes the characteristic weekly demand (with a total volumetric demand of 296m^3) from 278 residential units which are supplied by the centralised RWH system. The decentralised RWH system serves only 23 residential units and follows the profile in Fig. 5.9 adjusted to 8.3% of the demand from 278 residential units.

Fig. 5.9. **Non-potable demand profile** for the group of **278 residential units** over **a week-long period**. The pattern of peaks and troughs follows from probabilistic modelling of toilet and washing machine usage.

5.3 – Optimisation of parameters

The model was run using **storage fraction (S_f)** which is a dimensionless parameter that allows for equitable comparison of the centralised and decentralised system. S_f is defined by Eq. 11 which relates storage capacity (S), catchment area and mean annual rainfall (R_i) – in this case i denotes a year-long period (Campisano & Modica, 2012).

$$S_f = \frac{S}{A \cdot R_i} \quad [11]$$

The optimisation approach for tank size involved variance of the storage fraction with the three performance indicators listed in section 3.7: water savings efficiency, storm capture efficiency and loss factor. **Both YAS and YBS algorithms** were analysed. For each of these indicators, there is a trade-off between system performance and increased storage fraction, i.e., rising costs.

5.3.1 – Centralised system

Multiple simulations of the centralised RWH system were conducted yielding data which is reported in Fig. 5.10, 5.11 and 5.12 relating storage fraction with water savings efficiency, storm capture efficiency and loss factor. During the beginning of the optimisation process, the setpoint was kept at 90% of the total tank volume in order to prevent it from being a limiting factor at the expense of flood attenuation performance. Fig. 5.10 shows water savings efficiency reaching a maximum of 45%. Despite sharp increases in E_{WS} for low S_f values, there are diminishing returns for performance gains as S_f is increased further. For the centralised system, an S_f of 0.05 equates to a tank with a capacity of 356m³. Although such a system is beyond financial and even physical possibility, it demonstrates that tank size is not the limiting factor for further improvements in E_{WS} . There are two possible reasons for this; firstly, the insufficient supply of rainwater to the system relative to the expected demand; and secondly, a low setpoint causing large spillage volumes and therefore necessitating top-up from the mains to meet demand. Given that a setpoint of 90% was used for these initial simulations, the diminishing performance increases are likely due to the insufficient supply of rainwater, not tank sizing.

Fig. 5.10. The variance of storage fraction with water savings efficiency for a centralised system. The relationship between S_f and E_{WS} can be approximated by the logarithmic function, $E_{WS} = 4.5 \ln(S_f) + 56.7$ where $R^2 = 0.98$. E_{WS} approaches an upper limit of 45% as S_f is increased.

Stormwater capture efficiency data reported in Fig. 5.11 provides more evidence showing that diminishing performance increases are due to a lack of available rainwater. An E_{SC} of 91% is

reached with an S_f of 0.02, meaning that 91% of all harvested rainwater is used to satisfy demand whereas only 9% leaves the system as spillage. Although the E_{SC} is high, the corresponding water savings efficiency is only 40%; consequently 60% of demand is met by the mains supply at considerable expense.

Fig. 5.11. The variance of storage fraction with stormwater capture efficiency for a centralised system. The relationship between S_f and E_{SC} can be approximated by the logarithmic function, $E_{SC} = 10.2 \ln(S_f) + 128.4$ where $R^2 = 0.98$. E_{SC} approaches 100% with a storage fraction of 0.06.

In the centralised system, an S_f of 0.02 equates to a tank of volume 143m^3 . A centralised system at the Brabazon Hangar has the greatest potential to accommodate a single large tank, however it is unlikely to yield a good return on investment (ROI) if the supply of rainwater is insufficient. As emphasised throughout this report, the two most significant benefits of RWH systems are the non-potable water savings and flood attenuation. With a tank of volume 143m^3 , the reduced strain on the urban water system is beneficial with only 601m^3 of spillage for 6769m^3 of harvested rainwater over a year-long period; despite this, satisfying only 40% of non-potable demand is likely to be insufficient. Fig. 5.12 shows the ability of this centralised system to retain harvested rainwater with very low loss factors across a wide range of storage fractions even reaching 0% at an S_f of 0.05. Increased spillage drives the L_F and although low loss factors are preferential, spillage is only detrimental at times when the downstream drainage network is overwhelmed.

Fig. 5.12. The variance of storage fraction with loss factor for a centralised system. The relationship between S_f and L_F can be approximated by the logarithmic function, $L_F = -10.3 \ln(S_f) - 29.8$ where $R^2 = 0.97$. L_F reaches 0% with a storage fraction of 0.06.

Results reported in Fig. 5.10, 5.11 and 5.12 show that the YAS and YBS algorithms produce results that are almost identical. There is some difference in performance at low storage fractions (between 0.0001 and 0.0025) where the model using the YBS algorithm yields a greater water savings efficiency and a greater stormwater capture efficiency along with a lower loss factor; however, the differences in E_{WS} , E_{SC} and L_F are 5% at most and decrease to 0% as S_f reaches 0.005.

Generally, the results produced by models using YAS and YBS algorithms are significantly different at low tank volumes; a YAS model will give a conservative estimate of performance whilst a YBS model will give a liberal estimate (Ward et al., 2010). However, as the temporal resolution of rainfall and demand data increases the difference between YAS and YBS performance decreases. In the YBS algorithm, yield may be drawn from the spillage volume – this assumes that the spillage volume at each timestep is available to satisfy yield insofar as it occurs within the same timestep. This is a questionable assumption as in real-world systems, harvested rainwater will leave the system as spillage instantaneously if the tank is full. The validity of this assumption is poor for data with a large timestep as the spillage volume has longer to accumulate; thus, it has greater potential to be used as yield. At smaller timesteps this potential is reduced and therefore the difference between the tank levels at the end of each

timestep (due to the YAS and YBS models) is lessened. In this instance, daily rainfall levels for 2018 are being used in conjunction with hourly water demand volumes. To address the mismatch in temporal scale, the model averages the daily rainfall values equally across 24 hour-long segments. By artificially reducing the timestep of the rainfall data by a factor of 1/24 to correspond to the hourly demand data, the difference between the tank levels (due to the YAS and YBS algorithms) at the end of each timestep is greatly reduced. At an hourly temporal scale, the models perform similarly as evidenced in Fig. 5.10, 5.11 and 5.12. To show the effect of an increased temporal scale on performance, Fig. 5.13 reports the water savings efficiency for YAS and YBS models using daily demand and rainfall data.

Fig. 5.13. The variance of storage fraction with water savings efficiency for daily rainfall and demand data highlighting the effect of time step on YAS and YBS performance. The relationships between S_f and E_{SW} for the YAS and YBS models are approximated by logarithmic functions with R^2 values of 0.88 and 0.97 respectively.

At low storage fractions (small tank volumes) the YBS model clearly outperforms the YAS model with a water savings efficiency of 52.8% compared to 32.4% at a storage fraction of 0.15×10^{-3} . This 20.4% performance difference is significant and equates to water savings of $3,144\text{m}^2$ over the course of a year. Despite this saving, YAS performance sharply increases between storage fractions of 0.15×10^{-3} and 0.5×10^{-3} , eventually matching YBS performance at $S_f = 0.75 \times 10^{-3}$. Over this range there is an increased likelihood that the tank is full – this has a more adverse effect on a YAS system since the spillage volume is completely lost whereas a YBS system can recoup some of the spillage volume as yield. Beyond $S_f = 0.75 \times 10^{-3}$ this effect

diminishes as tank size increases and thus the likelihood of a full tank is reduced which reduces the propensity of large and frequent spillage volumes.

5.3.2 – Decentralised system

The same approach was applied to the decentralised system. Simulations were conducted producing data that related storage fraction with water savings efficiency, storm capture efficiency and loss factor (see Fig. 5.14, 5.15 and 5.16). To ensure consistency in the optimisation approach the setpoint was kept at 90% of the total tank volume in order to prevent it from being a limiting factor at the expense of flood attenuation performance. Since it is a dimensionless quantity, the storage fraction allows for comparison of performance indicators despite a difference in tank size.

Fig. 5.14. The variance of storage fraction with water savings efficiency for a decentralised system. The relationship between S_f and E_{WS} can be approximated by the logarithmic function, $E_{WS} = 9.47 \ln(S_f) + 96.3$ where $R^2 = 0.96$. E_{WS} approaches an upper limit of 70% as S_f is increased.

Fig. 5.14 shows the water savings efficiency, E_{WS} , approaching a limit of 72%. For storage fractions in the range 0.001 to 0.01, E_{WS} increases sharply since tank volume is the limiting factor. In this range, small increases in storage fraction lead to a large reduction of spillage volume throughout the year period as instances where the tank is full decreases. At some point, in the region where $S_f = 0.01$, the limited volume of harvested rainwater begins to dominate the relationship between S_f and E_{WS} . Further increases in tank size cause minor reductions of

spillage as few rainfall events can fill up the total capacity of the tank. With a S_f of 0.0075, a water savings efficiency of 36% is achieved.

Fig. 5.15. The variance of storage fraction with stormwater capture efficiency for a decentralised system. The relationship between S_f and E_{SC} can be approximated by the logarithmic function, $E_{SC} = 11.8 \ln(S_f) + 121.3$ where $R^2 = 0.97$. E_{SC} approaches an upper limit of 90% as S_f is increased.

Fig. 5.16. The variance of storage fraction with loss factor for a decentralised system. The relationship between S_f and L_F can be approximated by the logarithmic function, $L_F = -12.5 \ln(S_f) - 24.8$ where $R^2 = 0.96$. Initially, L_F decreases sharply and eventually approaches 7% with a storage fraction of 0.06.

5.3.3 – Optimisation of set point

In order to analyse the effect of set point on performance, the tank storage volume was held constant by setting the storage fraction to 0.01 for the centralised and 0.075 for the decentralised systems. Performance was evaluated for set points in the range 0.5 to 1.0. If set to 0.5, at the end of each timestep, any stored rainwater beyond $\frac{1}{2}$ of the tank’s capacity is spilled. Conversely, a set point of 1.0 will not cause any additional spillage.

Fig. 5.17. The variance of setpoint with water savings efficiency for a centralised system.

Fig. 5.18. The variance of setpoint with water savings efficiency for a decentralised system.

Fig. 5.17, 5.19 and 5.21 (left-hand side) pertain to the centralised system whilst Fig. 5.18, 5.20 and 5.22 (right-hand side) pertain to the decentralised system. In each figure, the performance indicators were calculated for two different rainfall time series. The daily rainfall time series for 2018 constitutes the ‘typical rainfall year’ whereas the ‘high rainfall month’ consists of a daily rainfall time series for November 2009 – the wettest month (in Bristol) in the entire 11-year dataset with a monthly rainfall total of 210.4mm. Setpoints are implemented in RWH systems to control the amount of available storage and therefore ensure that storage capacity is consistently available. More aggressive (lower) set points tend to have a detrimental effect on E_{WS} , E_{SC} and L_F during moderate rainfall regimes as the maintenance of spare storage reduces system performance without any upside. This effect on performance is still apparent during extreme rainfall regimes, however lower set points will increase the amount of rainwater retained during the event, thus reducing the stress on the downstream drainage network.

Fig. 5.19. The variance of setpoint with stormwater capture efficiency for a centralised system.

Fig. 5.20. The variance of setpoint with stormwater capture efficiency for a decentralised system.

Fig. 5.21. The variance of setpoint with loss factor for a centralised system.

Fig. 5.22. The variance of setpoint with loss factor for a decentralised system.

Each of Fig. 5.17 – 5.22 show decreases in system performance as the setpoint volume is reduced. This decrease in system performance for E_{WS} , E_{SC} and L_F does not exceed 6% for systems run with the extreme rainfall regime since tank volume is the limiting factor in each of these cases. System performance reduces more sharply when run using the moderate rather than extreme rainfall regimes. E_{WS} fell by 7% with the moderate regime applied to the centralised system compared to a drop of only 3% from the extreme regime (see Fig. 5.19). Drops in E_{WS} , E_{SC} and L_F may be due to higher spillage volumes. Spillage is derived from 2 sources. First, spillage from inflow to a full tank and second spillage due to a setpoint. When the model is run with the extreme regime the tank reaches maximum capacity for 68% of timesteps compared to only 24% with the moderate regime and thus the bulk of spillage is due to inflow exceeding tank volume rather than spillage due to a setpoint. Consequently, the effect of setpoint on the performance indicators will be reduced since the bulk of spillage is caused by inflow to a full tank. Furthermore, the reduction of setpoint volume causes a greater reduction in performance

of centralised systems compared to decentralised ones for the same reason. The centralised system was operated with an S_f of 0.01 compared to 0.0075 for the decentralised system; thus, the decentralised system is more likely to overflow as the bulk of spillage is due to inflow exceeding tank volume rather than spillage due to a setpoint. With all the available data, the setpoint cannot be reliably optimised as the extent to which changes in setpoint changes affect system efficiency is too low.

Successful optimisation of the setpoint requires detailed knowledge of tank volume dynamics during a rainfall event that poses a flood risk. Although this data is available within the 11-year time series, it is not of sufficient resolution. Continuing with analysis of the systems, a setpoint of 0.6 was used as a compromise between the performance indicators and flood attenuation capability although a better assessment of setpoint would have been possible with more data on extreme events.

5.3.4 – Comparison of optimised performance

Fig. 5.23. The variance of storage fraction with water savings efficiency for both the centralised and decentralised systems.

Although the centralised system has lower loss factors, this is largely insignificant as spillage reduction is only important during extreme events. Additionally, the decentralised system has higher water savings efficiency across the entire range of storage fractions due to a lower

demand to catchment area ratio at $0.85 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2$ compared to $1.53 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2$ for the centralised system. Relative to demand, the catchment from residential units is smaller than the catchment from the Brabazon Hangar which feeds the centralised system.

Fig. 5.24. The variance of storage fraction with stormwater capture efficiency for both the centralised and decentralised.

Fig. 5.25. The variance of storage fraction with loss factor for both the centralised and decentralised.

For the centralised system, with consideration given to E_{WS} , E_{SC} , L_F and the performance of YAS- and YBS-based models, a storage fraction of 0.01 was selected as the optimal value in order to counterbalance the impressive flood attenuation performance with poor water savings. The choice of algorithm was inconsequential due to similarity of their performance – the YAS model was selected. A lower storage fraction of 0.0075 was selected for the decentralised system due to the number of systems needed to satisfy demand (the centralised system supplies 12 times as many residential units as the decentralised system). Table 5.1 contains the optimised parameters and resulting indicators for the both systems.

Table 5.1. Optimised configuration for the centralised and decentralised RWH systems.

System Type	Overall Tank Size, V [m ³]	Water Savings Efficiency, E_{WS} [%]	Stormwater Capture Efficiency, E_{SC} [%]	Loss Factor, L_F [%]	Storage Fraction S_f	Algorithm
Centralised	71.2	35.7	81.3	18.7	0.01	YAS
Decentralised	8.0	47.1	59.3	40.7	0.0075	YAS

5.4 – Economic evaluation

Evaluation of a project’s business case requires consideration of the intricate details as well as the wider scope of the project – an ill-conceived and vague assessment based on inaccurate data and invalid assumptions often leads to disappointing value creation at best and substantial financial loss at worst.

5.4.1 – Savings (*value realisation*)

The value realisation of RWH systems occurs over long periods of time. Traditionally, this value is derived solely from mains water savings however this picture is no longer reflective of the economic case for RWH. The flood attenuation performance of active RWH systems can lead to sizeable savings on stormwater management networks – typical annual spending on flood management and damages in the UK amounts to £2.2 billion (Elliot Morley, 2017). Despite this, these cost savings are unfortunately very difficult to quantify without specific knowledge of the stormwater management system planned for the YTL development and therefore this economic evaluation will only focus on mains water savings.

Wessex Water (a subsidiary of YTL) is a residential water utility provider serving the South West of England. Future Filton residents are likely to use them as a provider, hence their price per cubic meter shall be used for the following evaluation. As of May 2020 this stands at £2.0058 per m³ (Wessex Water, 2020).

Fig. 5.26. Tank volume and mains water savings for a year-long period (in £ks) for the decentralised system in Table 5.1.

Fig. 5.27. Tank volume and mains water savings for a year-long period (in £ks) for the centralised system in Table 5.1.

The graphs in Fig. 5.26 and 5.27 report the cost savings from the decentralised and centralised systems respectively. These savings are proportional to E_{WS} hence why similar logarithmic behaviour is observed. As expected, savings increase along with increases in tank size and begin to flatten out as tank sizes reaches 15m³ for the centralised system and 150m³ for the decentralised system – for these tank sizes, annual savings are £1,430 and £12,200. For the optimised systems with volumes of 8.0m³ (decentralised) and 71.2m³ (centralised), savings are less at £1,280 and £11,200 respectively; however, in both cases the tank sizes are approximately half the volume, greatly reducing the initial capital investment required to construct the systems.

5.4.2 – System cost

The combined influence of several factors makes such an assessment a non-trivial undertaking. According to Gould, 1999, these factors are the limited availability of comparable cost information (particularly post-construction cost information), the lack of empirical information on the lifespan of components and the fluctuations in exchange rates between different jurisdictions. The picture is complicated further by the fact that relative costs are influenced by regional and local differences in service levels, the effect of economies of scale, quality of construction, quality of components and extent of operational maintenance and whether or not work is carried out by contractors.

The evaluation of total project cost is based on three key areas: capital expenditure including software and hardware (CapEX), operating and minor maintenance expenditure (OpEx), and the cost of capital (CoC).

CapEx falls under three categories: harvesting, storage and distribution. The harvesting costs entail the designation of catchment area as well as ensuring the maximum fraction of rainwater incident on the area enters the system - this cost is extremely dependent on situation. Storage costs are straightforward: the rainwater tank and earth movements (if necessary). Economies of scale do not appear to exist in Fig. 5.28, a linear relationship between cost and tank volume is shown. Although data for tanks with large storage volumes (in excess of 40m³) appear to rely on the topology of the natural environment, functions as reservoirs. This feature is not available for either system. Like harvesting costs, distribution costs are extremely situational – the distance and height differential between the tank and source of demand affects pumping requirements. For large centralised systems which distribute rainwater over a large area, these costs are considerable. Furthermore, higher numbers of residential units connected to a RWH system increase the complexity and drive costs upwards. The centralised system supplies 12 times more residential units than the decentralised system, therefore it is likely that the high distribution cost of the centralised system is offset by the additional cost involved in the construction of 12 decentralised units.

Fig. 5.28. Comparison of RWH system CapEx (encompassing labour and materials) with storage tank volume (Gould, 1999).

OpEx for RWH systems includes pump electricity consumption, pump repair/replacement, cleaning of catchment surface and water quality treatment items; however, finding OpEx data

that is applicable to a RWH system situated in the Filton Airfield development is difficult. It is likely that the centralised system will incur far greater pump electricity and repair/replacement costs due to the expanse of the distribution network, although the cost of maintenance for a single, large tank will be less the maintenance cost of 12 smaller tanks. Finally, the CoC (cost of capital) will include interest on credit used for the project and must be considered.

5.4.3 – Cost-benefit analysis

Capital expenditure, operational expenditure and the cost of capital may be compensated by benefits from water savings. **The Net Present Value (NPV)** model may be used to perform this analysis. The equation for NPV is given by Eq. 12 where B_t represents the benefits, C_t represents the costs, t refers to the period in which cash flow occurred and i is the discount rate.

$$NPV_T = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{(B_t - C_t)}{(1 + i)^t} \quad [12]$$

Benefit primarily derives from the volume of mains water saved at the specified rate of £2.0058 per m³. The capital expenditure required for a RWH system falls into three main areas: harvesting, storage and distribution. Although cost information for tank capacity is available in Fig. 5.28, the costs of harvesting and distribution are specific to the situation of the RWH system and at this stage many unknowns still remain. The NPV model uses a discount factor allowing the calculation of present value based on future cash flows or cost savings.

The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) is an alternative method of economic assessment. The BCR is the sum of discounted costs, divided by the sum of discounted benefits as they occur at time, t over the lifetime of a project, T . The BCR is calculated according to Eq. 13.

$$BCR_T = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{C_t}{(1 + i)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{B_t}{(1 + i)^t}} \quad [13]$$

The benefit-cost ratio is simply the ratio of benefits to costs, whereas the net present value is the benefits minus the costs (both metrics are discounted). NPV is considered to be a more useful metric since it is a monetary value rather than a ratio which is more commonly misinterpreted (Amos et al., 2018).

6 Conclusions and Future Work

The aim of this project was to produce a dynamic model for a rainwater harvesting system for the YTL urban development at Filton Airfield, optimise it and analyse its flood attenuation and mains water savings performance. The rainfall simulation was developed in order to produce synthetic rainfall data with an hourly timestep due to lack of available hourly data for the North Bristol region. Although the rainfall simulation accurately simulated the distribution of daily rainfall event intensity, it did not consider the effects of periodicity and seasonality. As a result, the output from the simulation could not be used to optimise RWH system parameters. In future, disaggregation models could be used to increase the resolution of rainfall data whilst maintaining accuracy.

Optimised storage fractions for the centralised and decentralised systems (0.01 and 0.0075) were a trade-off between the three performance indicators, tank volume and flood attenuation. These storage fractions equate to tank volumes of 71.2m^3 (centralised) and 8.0m^3 (decentralised). The decentralised system had greater water savings efficiency at 47.1% compared to only 35.7% for the centralised system. Data showed that the influx of harvested rainfall became a limiting factor at high tank volumes resulting in upper limits of 45% (centralised) and 70% (decentralised) for E_{WS} . This effect was more detrimental for the centralised system which has higher annual demand per m^2 of catchment area at $1.53\text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2$ compared to $0.85\text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2$ for the decentralised system.

Optimisation of the setpoint was difficult due to model limitations. Although setpoints over a range of 0.5 to 1.0 were tested, tank volume was the limiting factor in each case, which prevented the model from producing data which showed the relationship between setpoint and the three performance indicators. In the optimised systems, a setpoint of 0.6 was used, causing the tanks to maintain at least 40% spare storage volume. This spare capacity reduces the intensity of stormwater on the downstream drainage network. For all three indicators, varying setpoint over the above range never affected the performance indicators by more than 10%. In future, high resolution rainfall data should be used to accurately simulate the spillage volumes due to setpoints.

The final objective of this report was to use economic evaluation methods to assess the feasibility of the project. The cost savings due to decreased mains water demand were evaluated for both decentralised and centralised systems amounting to £1,280 and £11,200 per year. However, the scarcity of CapEx cost information for the harvesting, storage and distribution of RWH systems along with the inability to financially assess the impacts of stormwater reduction impeded the economic analysis. Groundwork that details the methods and considerations for economic evaluation is laid out in this report, leaving a framework for future study. Advancements in two areas are critical for the evaluation of the economic case of RWH systems at Filton. Firstly, communication with RWH suppliers is needed to obtain reliable and applicable CapEx and OpEx estimations. Secondly, to evaluate the economic value of stormwater reduction, extensive details of the drainage network at Filton would need to be obtained.

Acknowledgments

Throughout the development and evaluation of the RWH model built for this undergraduate research project I received a great deal of support and assistance from several individuals and groups, without which this research would not have been possible.

I would first like to thank my supervisor, Professor Jan Hofman whose expertise in the field of sustainable water management was invaluable in providing advice on RWH system design as well as the impetus for the research. I would also like to thank Dr Amy Kim for her consistent support and for kindly providing rainfall data sets directly from Filton Airfield.

I would like to thank the KWR Water Research Institute for the provision of their SIMDEUM software, allowing for an accurate simulation of domestic water usage.

Finally, I am immensely grateful to the members of the University of Bath's MASH (Maths & Statistics Help) Centre from whom I received guidance pertaining to the Monte Carlo simulation and KS test as well as instructive help on the Python code.

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Appendix A – Health & Safety

This undergraduate research project consisted of the development of a RWH system model in Python as well as data collection from online sources – no laboratory or hazardous work took place and consequently all health and safety considerations related to safe use of a computer.

Although there was a planned excursion to the Filton Airfield to collect rain meter readings, it did not take place. If this were to have gone ahead, a separate risk assessment would have been conducted.

Whilst working at a computer, correct posture and monitor positioning were employed to reduce the risk of computer-related injuries such as lumbar strain, carpal tunnel syndrome, disc injuries and eye strain. To achieve this end, regular breaks were taken, computer monitors were held slightly below eye level and seating with strong lumbar support was used.